

JAVA DASTURLASH MUHITIDA SHART OPERATORLARI (IF, SWITCH CASE)

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Java dasturlash tilidagi shart operatorlari if va switch case haqida ma'lumotlar hamda ularni qo'llashga oid misollar keltirib o'tilgan. Bu operatorlardan foydalanishda masalani qo'yilishiga qarab ularning birini ishlatish mumkinligi misollar tariqasida yoritilib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: if/else, int, switch, case, break, default, System.out.println.

ABSTRACT

In this article, information on the Java programming language Conditions and SWITCH CASE are given examples of them and their use. It is examined as an example of the use of these operators due to the application of the issue.

Keywords: if/else, int, switch, case, break, default, System.out.println.

Java, boshqa dasturlash tillari singari, bajarilishni boshqarish uchun shartli ifodalar va tsikllarni qo'llaydi.

if/else shartli ifodasi

if shartli ifoda quyidagi umumiy ko'rinishga ega:

if (shart) ifoda

Shartli ifodaning sharti qavs ichida bo'lishi kerak. Agar shart to'g'ri bo'lganda bir necha ifodalar bajarilishi kerak bo'lsa ular figurali qavslar ichiga olinishi kerak.

if (shart)

```
{  
ifoda 1;  
ifoda 2;  
}
```

Masalan:

```
if (x>25)
```

```
{  
tanNarx = 130; sifat  
= "yaxshi";  
}
```

dastur kodida agar x qiymati 25dan katta bo'lsa u holda shartli ifodaning

figurali qavslari ichida joylashgan barcha ifodalar bajariladi, ya'ni, tanNarx o'zgaruvchisining qiymati 130ga sifat o'zgaruvchisining qiymati "yaxshi" qiymatiga o'zgartiriladi. Quyida if shartli ifodaning blok sxemasi keltirilgan.

if shartli ifodaning umumiyroq ko'rinishi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

```
if (shart) ifoda1 else ifoda2
```

Ushbu ko'rinishda shartli ifodaning sharti to'g'ri bo'lsa ifoda1 bajariladi, agar shrt noto'g'ri bo'lsa ifoda2 bajariladi. Agar shartning xar bir xolatida bir necha ifodalar bajarilishi kerak bo'lsa ifodalar figurali qavslar ichida bo'lishi kerak.

```
if (shart){  
ifoda1;  
ifoda2;  
} else {  
ifoda3;  
ifoda4;  
}
```

Masalan:

```
if (x>25){ tanNarx  
= 130; sifat =  
"yaxshi";
```

```
} else { tanNarx =  
50;  
sifat = "qoniqarsiz";  
}
```

Dastur kodida agar x qiymati 25dan katta bo'lsa, tanNarx o'zgaruvchisini

ng

qiymati 130ga va sifat o'zgaruvchisining qiymati "yaxshi"ga o'zgaradi. Agar shartli ifodaning sharti bajarilmasa, ya'ni x qiymati 25dan kichik bo'lsa, tanNarx o'zgaruvchisining qiymati 50ga va sifat o'zgaruvchisining qiymati "qoniqarsiz"ga o'zgaradi.

if/else shartli ifodaning blok sxemasi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

Agar dasturda bir necha shartlarni ketma ket tekshirish kerak bo'lsa if/else if shartli ifodadan foydalanish mumkin:

```
if (shart1)
{
ifoda1;
} else if (shart2) {
ifoda2;
} else if (shart3) {
ifoda3;
}
```

Masalan, if
($x > 100$)
{
tanNarx = 250;

```
sifat = "alo"; } else if ( $x > 25$ ) {
tanNarx = 130;
sifat = "yaxshi";
} else if ( $x < 25$ ) {
```

```
tanNarx = 50;
sifat = "qoniqarsiz";
}
```

dastur kodida x qiymati 100dan katta bo'lsa tanNarx o'zgaruvchisining qiymati 250, sifat o'zgaruvchisining qiymati "alo", agar x qiymati 100dan kichik va 25dan katta bo'lsa tanNarx qiymati 130ga, sifat qiymati "yaxshi"ga, agar x qiymati 25dan kichik bo'lsa tanNarx qiymati 50ga, sifat qiymati "qoniqarsiz"ga o'zgaradi. x

if/else if shartli ifodaning blok sxemasi

if/else if shartli ifodaning blok sxemasi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

switch shartli ifoda. Switch shartli ifoda boshqaruvni blok ichida joylashgan, ma'lum belgiga ega ifodaga o'tkazib berish uchun xizmat qiladi. switch shartli ifoda quyidagi umumiy ko'rinishga ega:

```
switch (n)
{
case a: ifoda_1;           case b: ifoda_2;
...
default: ifoda_N;
}
```

Bu yerda n o'zgaruvchisining turi butun son, ya'ni int, bo'lishi kerak. Shartli ifoda bajarilganda n o'zgaruvchisi qabul qiladigan qiymat switch shartli ifodasining

case qatorida joylashgan qiymatiga teng bo'lsa ushbu qatordagi ifoda bajariladi. Agar, o'zgaruvchi qiymati case qatorlarining qiymatlariga teng bo'lmasa u holda default qatorining ifodasi bajariladi.

default qatori odatda switch shartli ifodaning oxirida joylashadi. default qatori

shartli hisoblanmaydi va yozilmasligi ham mumkin. Masalan,

```
int x = 2; switch
```

```
(x)
```

```
{
```

```
case 1: System.out.println("Birinchi ifoda");
```

```
case 2: System.out.println("Ikkinchi ifoda");
```

```
}
```

x o'zgaruvchisining qiymati 2 teng bo'lgani uchun 2 qiymatga ega case qatori bajariladi. Ushbu dastur kodi quyidagi matnni ekranga chiqarib beriladi:

Ikkinchi ifoda

Shuni ta'kidlab o'tish kerakki case qatorlari switch shartli ifodaning kirish nuqtasi hisoblanadi, ya'ni tegishli case qatori bajarilganda undan keyin joylashgan qatorlar ham bajariladi. Masalan:

```
int x = 2; switch
```

```
(x)
```

```
{
```

```
case 1: System.out.println("Birinchi qator");
```

```
case 2: System.out.println("Ikkinchi qator");
```

```
case 3: System.out.println("Uchinchi qator");
```

```
default: System.out.println("Default qatori");
```

```
}
```

Yuqoridagi dastur kodi bajarilganda ekranga quyidagi matn chiqarib beradi:Ikkinchi qator

Uchunchi qator

Default qatori

Agar switch shartli ifodasining faqatgina bir qatori bajarilishi kerak bo'lsa ushbu qator oxirisigacha bajarilish tartibini buzuvchi ifodadan, ya'ni break ifodasidan,foydalanish mumkin. Masalan:

```
int x = 2; switch
```

```
(x)
```

```
{
```

```
case 1:
```

```
System.out.println("Birinchi qator");
```

```
break;
```

```
case 2: System.out.println("Ikkinchi qator");
```

```
break; case
```


3:

```
System.out.println("Uchinchi qator");  
break;  
default: System.out.println("Default qatori");  
}
```

Yuqoridagi dastur kodi quyidagi matnni ekranga chiqarib beradi: Ikkinchi qator

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